

An Integrated Robotic Depalletizing System for Supermarkets' Backrooms

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Abstract—Depalletizing robotic systems are commonly deployed to automatize and speed up parts of logistic processes. Despite this, the necessity to adapt the preexisting logistic processes to the automatic systems often impairs the application of such robotic solutions to small business realities like supermarkets. Integrating a robotic system into the supermarket depalletizing process demands a high level of autonomy, based on strong perceptive, executive and gripping capabilities. This abstract describes an integrated robotic depalletizing system designed to be easily deployed into supermarket logistic processes. The system is described along with its main components, showing how the proposed framework performs in a real supermarket scenario.

Index Terms—Logistics, Intelligent and Flexible Manufacturing, Computer Vision for Automation, Grippers and Other End-Effectors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic logistics is the field of industrial robotics whose aim is to optimize the flow of goods both inside the manufacturing and large-scale distribution. Technological challenges are open for several scenarios, spreading from the unloading/loading to the palletizing/depalletizing of goods, as reported in [1]. In particular, depalletizing is the process of unloading an object, such as a corrugated carton on a pallet, in a defined pattern. This procedure is common in logistics where the goods are typically delivered inside cases, which can be of different dimensions or weights. This task is a hard and tiresome activity for human workers since they have to manually remove a huge number of weighty cases. Robotic depalletizing solutions increase productivity and are often deployed inside factories. In many industrial contexts, robotic depalletizing cells are typically tailored to specific products (having the same shape, same dimensions, and same appearance) and specific product lines. Such kind of context dramatically simplifies the executive, perceptive, and gripping capabilities required to the robotized system. On the other hand, in some logistic scenarios like supermarkets, the products are heterogeneous (different shapes, dimensions, and textures) and stored on *mixed pallets*, that are, pallets made of cases with different dimensions and textures. This abstract gives a brief description of an integrated robotic system that has been recently proposed in [2], [3], and [4] to operate in supermarkets' backrooms, as conceptually represented in Fig. 1. The system can recognize and flexibly depalletize cases from mixed pallets avoiding invasive sensors or structural changes in the logistic process. The

Fig. 1. Rendering of an ideal depalletizing cell with the gripper prototype attached to an industrial robot.

proposed robotic system is composed of 3 main subsystems: an innovative gripping system to grasp cases from different sides [2], a perceptive system that identifies, recognizes, and localizes cases on the pallet [3] and a strategy to schedule and orchestrate the depalletizing sequence [4].

II. THE INTEGRATED ROBOTIC DEPALLEITIZING SYSTEM

1) Gripping System: To obtain a design adaptable to different scenarios, the gripper proposed in [2] was developed considering the following requirements: *i)* the ability to grasp cases from top and side; *ii)* the ability to grasp cases placed over other cases; *iii)* the ability to grasp cases with dimensions in the range [15 – 50] cm; *iv)* the ability to grasp cases with weight up to 10 Kg; *v)* the automatic detection of the cases orientation using the embedded sensors; *vi)* the embedded detection of the case weight; *vii)* the automatic reconfiguration. The novel gripper is composed of two symmetric modules, each one equipped with a suction system and a fork, that can be reconfigured along the horizontal axis to adapt the gripper to cases with different dimensions. This design was chosen for the following reasons: *i)* the use of two different, independent and re-configurable modules allows the gripper to grasp cases of different dimensions, involving a single module for small cases and both modules for larger ones; *ii)* the use of forks allows to grasp cases from the bottom side by loading the case's weight on the forks itself during handling and not on the suction system; *iii)* cases with complex shapes (e.g. bottle

packages) or fragile structures (e.g. cases with easy openings) can be grasped from the side.

2) *Perceptive System*: The perceptive system proposed in [3] can be split in three components: *the cases database* (CDB); *the detection module* (DM); *the geometrical module* (GM). The CDB stores information regarding cases belonging to the pallet (the product barcode, the number of instances of the case in the pallet, the dimensions of the case, the images of the faces if the case is textured). The DM detects cases from RGB-D data using a *feature detection* algorithm for textured faces, as well as, an *image segmentation* algorithm for untextured ones. Then, an *iterative methodology* is deployed to reconstruct the planar model of each detected face in 3D. The GM identifies detected cases using a *geometrical matching* algorithm which compares the dimensions of the candidate face with those of the faces stored in the CDB. Finally, the GM localizes the identified cases via a *geometrical localization* algorithm which estimates their pose given the position and the orientation of the detected face, as well as, the dimensions of the related case, stored in the CDB.

3) *Depalletizing Strategy*: Since the configuration and the pose of each element of the mixed pallet are not known in advance, the sequence in which cases are taken has to be decided online depending on perceptual information. The depalletizing strategy proposed in [4] defines a suitable function that associates a priority to cases considering their positions on the pallet. Such a function is based on a heuristic: take cases from the upper part to the base and from the sides to the center of the pallet to guarantee that the base of the pallet is always larger than the summit and the stability of the structure is not compromised. Moreover, since the pallet is positioned in front of the robot, frontal cases have been slightly prioritized to support manipulability. Besides their position, the priority of the cases is also affected by the requests that can be asynchronously provided to the system in response to specific logistic necessities.

III. SUPERMARKET BACKROOM SCENARIO

In the considered application, typical of supermarkets' backroom, the products are collected into cases that have to be stored from the original pallet to a set of generic target locations (like trolleys or shelves). The real cell, depicted in Fig. 2, includes a robot manipulator (6-DOF Kuka kr60) endowed with the described suction-based gripping end-effector and an RGB-D camera (Intel Realsense D435). In our design, the pallet is positioned in front of the robot, allowing the manipulator to reach the cases and to move them toward the target locations, or to move cases from one location to another, while the RGB-D camera is placed between the robot and the pallet. The gripper has been tested in [2] considering a set of 57 grasping trials over 19 different cases. The cases have been selected to have different shapes and dimensions, with weights in a range of [0.5, 10] Kg. Each test has been repeated considering different approaching sides (lateral, frontal, and upper side) and for the 89.47% of trials the system was able to grasp the case from at least one side. The recognition and

Fig. 2. Real depalletizing cell.

localization capabilities of the system have been tested in [3], using 9 cases organized in 10 different configurations of the mixed pallet. The experiments carried out show an accuracy of $\approx 98\%$ over a set of 180 recognitions to be performed. The system guarantees a precision below the tolerance imposed by the gripper requiring a maximum estimation error of 0.020 m on the axes y_c . To test the depalletizing strategy, 500 simulated executions have been considered in [4], where both the pallet configuration and the sequence of requests have been randomly generated. The system has to depalletize cases following their scores while avoiding collisions due to occlusions. In the simulated experiments, all executions have been accomplished while the average number of actions needed to satisfy a request ranges between 11.14 and 7.13 depending on the trade-off between stability-oriented and request-oriented strategies.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this abstract, an integrated robotic depalletizing system has been presented. The system has been deployed in a real supermarket scenario considering a typical backdoor setting. A suitably designed adaptive gripping module and a perceptive system allow the framework to operate with mixed pallets (*i.e.*, pallets made by cases of different shapes and textures). Moreover, a peculiar depalletizing strategy was designed to coordinate manipulation activities while avoiding collisions and falling of cases. The integrated system has been tested for different pallet configurations showing satisfactory results in terms of grasping capabilities as well as successful recognition/localization of cases and satisfied requests.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Echelmeyer, A. Kirchheim, and E. Wellbrock, "Robotics-logistics: Challenges for automation of logistic processes," in *2008 IEEE International Conference on Automation and Logistics*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 2099–2103.
- [2] G. A. Fontanelli, G. Paduano, R. Caccavale, P. Arpentì, V. Lippiello, L. Villani, and B. Siciliano, "A reconfigurable gripper for robotic autonomous depalletizing in supermarket logistics," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 4612–4617, 2020.
- [3] P. Arpentì, R. Caccavale, G. Paduano, G. Andrea Fontanelli, V. Lippiello, L. Villani, and B. Siciliano, "Rgb-d recognition and localization of cases for robotic depalletizing in supermarkets," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 6233–6238, 2020.
- [4] R. Caccavale, P. Arpentì, G. Paduano, A. Fontanelli, V. Lippiello, L. Villani, and B. Siciliano, "A flexible robotic depalletizing system for supermarket logistics," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 4471–4476, 2020.